

(REVIEW ARTICLE)

Survey of some plant for the Razzaza Lake and adjacent areas in Iraq

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Abstract

The study showed that there are (28) plant families present in Al-Razzaza Lake. The families are (Amaranthaceae, Amaryllidaceae, Aizoaceae, Apiaceae, Apocynaceae, Asteraceae, Brassicaceae, Boraginaceae, Capparaceae, Caryophyllaceae, Cistaceae, Colchicaceae, Convolvulaceae, Cynomoriaceae, Fabaceae, Frankeniaceae, Lamiaceae, Liliaceae, Malvaceae, Orobanchaceae, Plantaginaceae, Poaceae, Polygonaceae, Ranunculaceae, Solanaceae, Tamaricaceae, Typhaceae, Zygophyllaceae). Asteraceae family is the largest number of species found in abundance in this lake, followed by the Fabaceae family.

Keywords: Survey; Plant; Razzaza; Lake; Iraq

1. Introduction

Razzaza Lake linked with Al- Habbaniya Lake from the north by the narrow canal which run through semi-desert, named the canal of Sin Al-Thibban [1]. Al-Razzaza was a large and deep lake, currently, it has greatly reduced in size and is also characterized by very high levels of salinity and in various concentrations, and the main reason for its increase during the past ten years is the lack of water and high evaporation during that period [2]. Biodiversity is one of the most important natural resources for nations and peoples, and they have the responsibility to protect it A healthy biome is responsible for a wide range of operations and environmental services that life cannot sustain Without it, such as loading organic waste, purifying the atmosphere and protecting the soil from erosion Biodiversity studies should be given priority For the affected areas because they need special care and a number of quick measures that will reduce the negative effects [3,4]. The climate change that the world has been going through for several decades has led to a change in both air and water And soils have contributed to changing the biogeochemical cycles, which Reflected its impact on biodiversity in many regions of the world [5,6]

2. Material and methods

The study of plant biodiversity for any region must rely on recent data that can occur It is based on field surveys, in addition to the researcher's observations with the published rules Compiled checklist species data and inventories Data from these sources are compiled into special tables.

3. Results and discussion

The results show that, according to the table 1, there is a great diversity of plants in this lake, which is one of the very important lakes. The Plants, like all living organisms in this lake, are distributed in varying and different numbers, and plant species may be densely spread in one place, and may be distributed in simple scattered numbers, or may be concentrated in specific places. There are many monocot and dicot plants (Figure 1). There are many widespread plant

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families that have been diagnosed according to the important characteristics of each plant family and using the taxonomic keys. It has been observed that many plant families flourished in this aquatic environment and continued to live (Table 1). The results showed that Asteraceae family is the highest number of species spread in the lake, followed by Fabaceae family. They are one of the largest plant families prevalent in the aquatic environment as well as on land, and they are characterized by a large number of plant species. While there are plant families that were characterized by a small number of their species and perhaps a low distribution in that environment, due to the fact that the environment may not be suitable for their growth and existence [7,8]. The difficult environmental conditions, climatic changes, air pollution, and other reasons helped the disappearance of a number of plant families [9,10,11]. It has been observed that the dicotyledonous plant families are more widespread than the monocotyledonous plants. It was also noted that number of plant species belonging to a certain family when comparing the results with previous researchers [12,13,14], noted that these species began to disappear for environmental reasons or because of the conditions of the war. Asteraceae family has many plant species that have existed for a long time in this lake and are still abundant. It was also noted that there are plant species that are always near other species. This lake was distinguished from other lakes by the diversity of its plants, as well as insects, birds and other living creatures, as it provided them with the appropriate environment for living. It has been observed that some organisms have disappeared due to difficult conditions, but they have returned to this distinctive lake after the availability of natural conditions and the return of organisms to live in it. There are many lakes in the country, but this lake differs because the plant diversity in it is large and many, and it is one of the very important places in the country. Therefore, its study has contributed to clarifying the true picture of the plant diversity in it and its importance to humans and other living creatures in this lake.

Table 1 The names of the plant families and the number of species in each family

No.	species	The Family
1	7	Amaranthaceae
2	2	Amaryllidaceae
3	2	Aizoaceae
4	2	Apiaceae
5	2	Apocynaceae
6	12	Asteraceae
7	7	Brassicaceae
8	3	Boraginaceae
9	2	Cyparaceae
10	4	Caryophyllaceae
11	2	Cistaceae
12	2	Colchicaceae
13	2	Convolvulaceae
14	2	Cynomoriaceae
15	10	Fabaceae
16	2	Frankeniaceae
17	2	Lamiaceae
18	2	Liliaceae
19	2	Malvaceae
20	4	Orobanchaceae
21	5	plantaginaceae
22	5	Poaceae
23	2	Polygonaceae

24	2	Ranunculaceae
25	2	Solanaceae
26	2	Tamaricaceae
27	2	Typhaceae
28	3	Zygophyllaceae

Figure 1 Species ratio for each plant family

4. Conclusion

The results of the research showed that there is a distinct plant diversity in Al-Razzaza Lake and that there is a discrepancy in the number of plant species belonging to each family that was diagnosed. The number of species is greatly affected by environmental conditions and their adaptation to difficult conditions.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

No Conflict of interest.

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